

Manuscript title: Increased intake of tree forage by moose is associated with intake of crops rich in non-structural carbohydrates

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Bayesian analyses – general model structure

The differences in the effect of different predictors can be directly quantified by subtracting the posterior distributions (A-B) within the JAGS model structure. Here we describe the Bayesian model used to estimate the probability of spruce being present in moose rumens (recent intakes) based on prior consumption of energy-dense and natural food groups (faecal data). Data are indexed to ‘i’ at the observation level and to ‘j’ for the predictions. The priors were chosen to be vague (minimally informative) to allow the data to determine their shape and range. Beta coefficients were centered on zero to avoid influencing whether their effects were negative or positive. For additional details see the BUGS code below. AROW refers to the broadleaved tree species aspen, rowan, oak and willow (see main text).

Spruce presence_i ~ *Binomial*(n_i, p_i)
logit(p_i) = α + β₁BS_i + β₂Api_i + β₃AROW_i
α ~ *Normal*(0,0.00001)
β₁₋₃ ~ *Normal*(0,0.00001)

Bayesian analyses –JAGS (BUGS) code to implement the model

```
## BUGS code (implemented in JAGS, Plummer 2003)
## Data supplied to the model:
# nobs = number of observations
# Picea = spruce presence in rumen data (0=absent, 1=present)
# BS = proportion of Beta vulgaris & Solanum tuberosum (sugar beet & potato) in the
faecal # data
# Api = proportion of Apioideae (carrots) in the faecal data
# AROW = proportion of AROW tree species in the faecal data
# x.pred = a vector corresponding to the range of the predictors BS,Api, & AROW

model{

#likelihood

  for(i in 1:nobs){

    Picea[i] ~ dbin(p[i],1)

#process model

    logit(p[i])<-alpha + b1*BS[i] + b2*Api[i] + b3*AROW[i]
  }
}
```

```

#priors
alpha~dnorm(0,0.00001)
b1~dnorm(0,0.00001)
b2~dnorm(0,0.00001)
b3~dnorm(0,0.00001)

#predictions
for(j in 1:length(x.pred)){
  logit(out.p_BS[j])<-alpha + b1*x.pred[j] + b2*mean(Api) + b3*mean(AROW)
  logit(out.p_Api[j])<-alpha + b2*x.pred[j] + b1*mean(BS) + b3*mean(AROW)
  logit(out.p_AROW[j])<-alpha + b3*x.pred[j] + b1*mean(BS) + b2*mean(Api)
  diff_BS_Api[j] <- out.p_BS[j] - out.p_Api[j]
  diff_BS_AROW[j] <- out.p_BS[j] - out.p_AROW[j]
}
}

```

References used

Plummer, M. 2003. JAGS: A program for analysis of Bayesian graphical models using Gibbs sampling. Pages 1-10 *in* Proceedings of the 3rd international workshop on distributed statistical computing. Vienna, Austria.